

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Community Cluster

On-Site Documentation

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SC Decision: 24.05.2024

Bodies Involved: TA1, TA5, CC Building Research and Preservation, CC Data Capture and Creation

External Linking: Baureka, VLA (esp. Kommission für Archäologie und Informationssysteme)

Subject & Objective

The CC "On-Site Documentation" covers the broad range of data generation and data management activities associated with archaeological and heritage conservation primary documentation within the research community. The archaeological and heritage management data collected in this process is fundamentally dependent on the type of exploration methods used, the associated research questions and other factors. The heterogeneous data generated in this way is a characteristic feature of the scientific research landscape.

The cluster is focused at the needs of those working in the field research sector regardless of their academic education and research focus. This includes both the documentation of finds and findings in situ as well as activities that are directly connected to excavations, such as primary find processing. The cluster therefore primarily supports discussions, e.g. on data structures and raw data processing within primary documentation, both method and platform-independent and specific, and contributes these to the other bodies of NFDI4Objects. With regard to the data processes in 3D documentation (e.g. SfM-Technique) in field research activities, this also includes the 3D documentation of stratigraphic units (e.g. features, profiles, plana), individual objects and large-scale natural structures (terrain models, etc.).

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Out of Scope

RDM-relevant topics in connected evaluation steps that go beyond the primary find processing, such as material and dating analyses or finely referenced typologies, are not taken into account in this respect, unless the information is indispensable for understanding the primary documentation data. Scientific analysis methods in field research primary documentation should be dealt with in cooperation with the specialist bodies of NFDI4Objects. The same applies to other subsequent processes, such as inventorying and other collection-related activities.

Long-term archiving and the handling of raw data relating to the primary documentation data should be carried out together with the thematically assigned NFDI4Objects bodies.

Preserved architectural structures form an essential part of the archaeologically tangible features. The cluster cooperates closely with the CC "Building Research and Preservation" on the relevant cross-cutting topics. If the RDM-relevant topics are foremost connected to structures primarily located in the field of historical building research, these should be addressed in by the CC "Building Research and Preservation".

Intended Work Results

The cluster serves to discuss white papers and tools developed in sub-working groups and will take up and structure other topics proposed by the community.

The following focus points are initially planned to be addressed in TWGs:

- Development of common standards and concepts for the RDM of the digital documentation of archaeological excavations and prospections, especially with regard to survey and attribute data.
- Method-specific standards for sustainable RDM, e.g. in excavation documentation using SfM-photogrammetry.
- Standardization and mapping of existing vocabularies in the area of application of digital primary documentation in close cooperation with the N4O bodies.
- Standardization of data, metadata and data models for primary documentation.
- Development of RDM standards in the associated find processing and cataloging of find objects, e.g. laser-aided-profiler (LAP), etc.